

Research Article

Comparative Study of Physical Composition of Some Honey Samples in Ibadan Metropolis

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Abstract

The study analysed seven honey samples. The honey samples used for the research are as follows: sample A – Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan, sample B – pure honey, sample C – Mr Honey, sample D – Taraba, sample E – Sokoto honey, sample F – Saki honey, sample G – natural honey. The following variables were analysed: pH refractive index, ash content, % purity, viscosity, specific gravity and colour. The colour of honey is very important. It is the colour that determines the commercial status of the honey; the refractive index has to do with the moisture content of the honey. The mean ash content of the various honey samples was 0.375% with a range of 0.241 – 0.3875%. Saki honey sample had the lowest ash content of 0.4810. These values are in conformity with the mean ash content of the US honey (0.169%) with a range of 0.20 – 10.28%. The colour of sample B, C and G which had undergone some levels of processing were brighter, while sample (A, D, E and F) were darker with range of (0.8625 – 1.2950). The average price per litre of processed sample (B, C and G) (1,250 naira) were higher than processed samples (D, E and F) (666.00 naira). The results also show that the geographical location does not affect the quality of the honey. Good packaging and processing will enhance the acceptability of the unprocessed honey and consequently lead to higher income.

Keywords: Honey, physical properties, refractive index, FRIN

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Introduction

Honey is a popular sweetener throughout the world; it is made by bees generally from nectars extracted from the nectarines of flowers. From ancient's time, honey was used both as natural sweetener and a healing agent (National Honey Board 2002).

Honey is a delicious food. It is high in carbohydrates and adds useful varieties to diets such as fructose and glucose, it is more readily digestible than cane sugar. Honey varies in taste, aroma and colour according to its source.

Many societies have an important place in traditional food preparation and is also viewed as a source of special nutrition for children although it should not be feed to young babies. Honey is widely used as a medicine and is highly prized for this reason. It is often regarded as a special tonic to food when eating during illness.

Honey has three biological factors which account for its antibiotic activities, which are as follow:

- i. Honey absorbs water and so it is capable of killing bacteria by dehydrating them. It also means that honey is sterile as most micro-organism cannot survive it.
- ii. Presence of enzymes which produces hydrogen peroxide that kills bacteria.
- iii. Honey is acidic (Richard, 1999)

Honey is farmed and used all over the world. Initially local farmers harvested the honey from the wild but today apiculture is wild spread industry in many parts of the world (Adesukanmi and Oyelami, 1994).

Honey has been used for gastrointestinal ailments, such as gastric ulcers, in which there is hyperacidity, the honey is thought to act by first healing surface of the gastric mucosa and secondly, by promoting the general building of the body and particularly the nervous system. Honey is a basic ingredient of several medicines, including cough syrup; the high fructose content of honey speed up alcohol metabolism in sobering drunken patients.

It is a known fact that honey possesses nutritional health benefits and healing properties, hence most people do purchase any type of honey even at high cost for utilization without adequate information about the quality of such honey. Considering the roles played by honey as a food compliment, raw material, medicine etc, it is

obvious that honey is very important to man. The increasing economic and domestic uses to which honey is being used and the non-challant attitude of people who just consume any kind of honey without adequate information about their quality makes this study a necessity. Therefore the research is aimed to compare the physical properties of selected honey samples in Ibadan.

Materials and method

Seven (7) honey samples were randomly selected in some markets in Ibadan Oyo State. Ibadan is with an estimated population of one million twenty two thousand and fifty nine (Nigeria population census, 2007) and it is the largest city in Southern of Sahara. Ibadan falls in the rainforest zone of Nigeria and has vegetation that supports luxuriant growth of both arable and tree crops, these crops in turns produce enough nectar that can support high population of bees in the production of honey in the area. Ibadan is inhabited mainly by Yoruba speaking people though other tribes have settled in the areas as a result of inter-tribal marriages and economic activities.

Procurement of Honey

A total of seven (7) honey samples were randomly selected at various selected markets in Ibadan and labeled as follows:

- Sample A : Federal College of Forestry (F.C.F)
- Sample B : Pure honey
- Sample C : Mr Honey
- Sample D : Taraba honey
- Sample E : Sokoto honey
- Sample F : Saki honey
- Sample G : Natural honey

Determination of Ash

Apparatus: Porcelain crucible, a desiccator, analytical balance and a furnace.

Determination: 2ml of the samples were weighed into a porcelain crucible. This was transferred into the muffled furnace set at 550 °C and left for about 24 hours. About 100 °C in air, then room temperature in a desiccator and weighed. This was done in duplicate.

The percentage ash was calculated from the formula below:

$$\% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{\text{Weight of ash}}{\text{Original weight sample}} \times \frac{100}{1} \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Determination for Refractive Index

The refractive index measurements were done with an abbe refractometer. The refractometer sample compartment was made at room temperature (28 °C). The electrical conductivity measurements were done at 25 °C using pH/Conductivity meter model 20 (Denyer instrument). The instrument was calibrated using 0.01M KCL (potassium chloride solution).

Determination of pH

The pH was measure using a digital pH meter model Hannan Instrument (HI) 8519.

Colour Determination

The colour of the samples was determined using the lovibond comparator.

Viscosity Determination

20ml slurry of each sample was prepared and transferred into a visco-pipette. The flow rate was measured after the slurry has reached the bulb of the pipette. The stop watch was used to measure the droppings from the descending of the bulb of the visco-pipette.

Total time taken in seconds to descend through the bulb of the seconds was taken as the time for the visco-pipette was taken as the time for the flow. Viscosity was calculated by using the formula.

$$\text{Viscosity} = \frac{\text{Volume of slurry}}{\text{Time taken to flow in (s)}} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Results and Discussion

The result of the honey physical properties such as the colour, pH, refractive index and the ash contents respectively are presented in Table 1. The pH of the honey samples fall within the range of established codex standard of honey (3.6 – 5.6) pure honey had the highest acidity (4.5900) while Mr. Honey has the lowest acidity (5.5900). These values are comparable to the pH values (3.4 – 6.1) of the honey of the United State of American (White, 1975).

Table 1: Showing colour density, pH, percentage ash and refractive index of the selected honey samples in Ibadan.

Samples	Colour	pH	Refractive Index	Ash content %
A	0.8625	5.4450	1.5032	0.4810
B	1.3830	4.5900	1.4965	0.3875
C	1.2525	5.5900	1.4937	0.4110
D	0.9775	4.6250	1.5017	0.3535
E	1.2950	5.5700	1.4975	0.2880
F	1.2275	5.5400	1.4977	0.2410
G	1.3840	5.500	1.5019	0.2875
Mean	1.1974	5.2729	1.4989	0.3499
Sd	0.2013	0.4568	0.0000	0.0265

Where; Sd – Standard deviation; A - Federal College of Forestry (F.C.F); B - Pure honey; C - Mr Honey; D - Taraba honey; E - Sokoto honey; F - Saki honey; G - Natural honey

The refractive index of honey is the rapid, accurate and simple measure of its moisture content (White 1975). White (1975) gave the following relationship between moisture content and refractive index of honey.

$$\text{moisture content: } \frac{1.7930 - \text{Long}_{(n_{20}-1)}}{0.002243} \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where n_{20} is the refractive index measure at 20 °C. If the refractive index is measured above 20 °C, 0.00023 per °C is added before using the above relationship. The honey samples tested had similar values with respect to refractive index. The mean ash content of the various honey samples are 0.375% with a range of 0.241 – 0.3875%. Saki honey sample had the lowest ash content – 0.241 while Forestry honey had the highest ash content – 0.4810. These values are inconformity with the mean ash content of U.S honey (0.169%) with a range 0.20 – 1.028% (Adebisi *et al.*, 2004)

Colour is very important; it is the colour that does more than anything else in the determination of its commercial use and value darker honeys are most often put to individual use while the lighter colour honeys are marketed directly for consumption (Richard, 1999). The samples B, C, G which had undergone some levels of processing have the higher values and they appear brighter.

The raw honey samples (A, D, E and F) had the lowest values signifying that they are darker than the processed honey. On the average honey from the north, and south did not show appreciable difference with respect to variables tested.

Table 2: Showing the price per litre of the selected honey samples.

Honey samples	Quantity / litres	Price (N)
A Forestry honey (FCF)	1	1,200
B Pure honey	1	1,200
C Mr. honey	1	1,000
D Taraba honey	1	800
E Sokoto honey	1	600
F Saki honey	1	600
G Natural honey	1	1,500

The prices of the various honey samples per litre are presented in Table 2. Sample B, C and G which are the processed honey are more expensive than the unprocessed honey samples with the exception of the sample A which is forestry honey. Perhaps the high cost of forestry honey could be due to the fact that forestry is a research Institute and the potential buyers are educated. The sample D, E and F which are less expensive or cheaper than the processed one. The higher cost of processed honey could be attributed to cost incurred at various stages of processing operations.

Table 3: Showing percentage purity, viscosity (ml/min) and specific gravity of the selected honey samples.

Samples	%purity	Viscosity	Spec. gravity (g/ml)
A	91.680	5.100	1.114
B	91.760	5.300	1.118
C	92.850	4.800	1.122
D	96.850	2.900	1.137
E	90.460	4.900	1.115
F	90.530	5.000	1.117
G	94.380	5.000	1.144
Mean	92.640	4.370	1.120
Sd	5.241	1.259	0.000

The sample D, which is the Taraba honey has the highest % purity while the sample E, which is Sokoto honey has the lowest % purity and the rest of the Sample A, B, C, F and G are almost the same in % purity.

Viscosity ml/mm of the sample B, which is the pure honey, is the highest and sample G, which natural honey has the lowest viscosity ml/mm. It is the sample B, A and F that is higher than mean viscosity ml/mm of the honey samples. The specific gravity of the honey samples are almost the same, with the range of (1.114 – 1.137) having the mean of (1.120). The specific gravity is similar.

Conclusion and Recommendations

For Nigeria to have a place in the list of official honey exporters, it's necessary that the qualities of honey produce in the country should be determined. The result of such analysis will help in the formulation of policies on bee keeping and honey products in Nigeria. Although the variables tested is just part of properties of the honey samples. Hence, this conclusion will only be valid only when other properties are available. The result of this study did not show any appreciable differences in the qualities of these samples. It is therefore necessary to embark on better processing and packaging in order to achieve higher sales and income. It had been discovered from this study that the physical values or component of internationally honey and the locally produced honey have no significant difference, the producers should improve their processing and packaging process and it is recommend that the buyer should buy and add more quality to the locally produced honey.

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